

lenedioxy dibenzoyl methane (VI) which on dehydrocyclisation with acetic acid and sodium acetate furnished the required 6,7-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyflavone (I), identical with the natural sample.

- (IV) $R^1 - R^2 - H$
 (V) $R^1 - H; R^2 - CO.C_6H_5$
 (VI) $R^1 - CO.C_6H_5$ (3,4-methylenedioxy).
 $R^2 - H$

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord model 577 spectrophotometer.

2-(3',4'-Methylenedioxybenzoyloxy)-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (V): A solution of 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (2.0 g) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was heated with 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoyl chloride (2.24 g) (prepared from 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoic acid, 2.0 g) at 100° for 1 hr and the reaction product was poured in ice-water. Solid crystals separated out, which was filtered, washed with dil.HCl and water, and crystallised from acetone as white crystals, m.p. 175-76°. (Found : C, 62.71 ; H, 4.82. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79 ; H, 4.68%). It did not give ferric reaction and was insoluble in cold aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%).

2-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxydibenzoyl methane (VI): A solution of V (2.5 g) in dry pyridine (20 ml) was heated with stirring with powdered potassium hydroxide (3.0 g) at 60°. In about 1 hr the potassium salt of the β -diketone separated out as yellow solid. The stirring was continued for 2 hr more and then acidified with dil. HCl. Yellow solid separated out which was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 184-185°. (Found : C, 62.74 ; H, 5.01 . $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79 ; H, 4.68%). It gave positive ferric reaction and dissolved in cold aqueous NaOH (10%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyflavone (Milletenin-C) (I): A mixture of the β -diketone (1.0 g),

fused sodium acetate (1.0 g) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 hr and then concentrated under reduced pressure to a small volume. It was then poured in ice water. The flavone (0.8 g) separated out and crystallised from amyl alcohol as colourless crystals, m.p. 251-52°(lit.¹, m.p. 252-53°). (Found : C, 66.21; H, 4.41. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 66.25; H, 4.32%). 100 MHz NMR, (TMS as internal standard) ($CDCl_3$, δ): 4.04, 4.06 (s, 6H, $2 \times OCH_3$), 6.12 (s, 2H, O- CH_2 -O), 6.6 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.32-6.74 (m, 3H, aromatic protons), 7.38 (m, 1H, C-5 periproton), 7.58 (m, 1H, H-6'). IR(KBr): 1640 ($>C=O$), 1610, 1510 cm^{-1} (aromatic $C=C$).

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References

1. H. KHAN and A. ZAMAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1974, 30, 2811.
2. A. C. JAIN and R. KHAZANCHI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16B, 1125.

Nitrogen Heterocyclic Analogous of Cannabinoids. Part-I : Synthesis of 6H-Indolo[1,2-C] [1,3]-benzoxazine Systems and Evaluation of Their Biological Activities

SURESH C. SHARMA*, M. P. SWAMI and R. C. SHARMA**

Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

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EFFORTS have recently been made to prepare nitrogen containing analogous of the cannabinoids to modify the pharmacological profile. Pyridobenzoxazine derivatives (I), synthesized by Nitya Anand *et al*^{1,2} as a model compound, containing a nitrogen atom at the ring junction of the pyran and alicyclic ring of tetrahydrocannabinol seemed to be of great interest for studying structure-activity relationship in this class of compounds. It was, therefore, thought that molecules having mixed features of cannabinoids (rings A and B) and that of

indole nucleus with nitrogen as part of both ring B and C would be of pharmacological interest. This

*Author for correspondence, **Department of Zoology.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF 6H-INDOLO[1,2-C] [1,3]BENZOXAZINE DERIVATIVES

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
1	H	Cl	54.0	138	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO	72.10 (71.94)	5.10 (4.95)	5.00 (4.92)
2	Cl	H	54.8	152-53	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO	72.00 (71.94)	5.10 (4.95)	4.90 (4.92)
3	H	Br	62.0	166-67	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrNO	62.45 (62.26)	4.30 (4.37)	4.45 (4.34)
4	Br	H	58.2	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrNO	62.50 (62.26)	4.40 (4.37)	4.40 (4.34)
5	H	OH	42.6	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NO ₂	77.25 (76.94)	5.80 (5.63)	5.50 (5.25)
6	OH	H	40.4	72-73	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NO ₂	77.10 (76.94)	5.80 (5.63)	5.40 (5.25)

led to the synthesis of 6H-indolo[1,2-C] [1,3]benzoxazine systems (II).

Substituted acetophenones of *p*-chlorophenol, *m*-chlorophenol, *p*-bromophenol, *m*-bromophenol, resorcinol and hydroquinone were treated with phenylhydrazine in boiling acetic acid to obtain their respective phenylhydrazones. However, when 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone was treated with phenylhydrazine under similar conditions, it failed to produce the desired hydrozone and, therefore, the hydroxyl groups were protected by treating with dimethylsulphate in presence of alkali in order to obtain 2,5-dimethoxyacetophenone. The compound was then treated with phenylhydrazine to get 2,5-dimethoxyacetophenonephenylhydrazone.

The hydrozones were treated with polyphosphoric acid at 120-40° to afford 2-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)indoles⁹. The ir spectra contained broad absorption bands in the region 3400-3175 cm⁻¹ due to νOH and νNH vibrations.

2-(2',5'-Dimethoxyphenyl)indole was heated with pyridine hydrochloride at 120° for 2 hr to procure 2-(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)indole.

The indoles thus obtained were treated with dry acetone in presence of *p*-toluenesulphonylchloride to obtain substituted 6H-indolo[1,2-C] [1,3]benzoxazine derivatives⁴ (Table 1). Their structures were confirmed by elemental analyses and by the absence of the νNH stretching vibrations in their ir spectra.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were recorded on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Acetyl derivatives of substituted phenols were subjected to Fries rearrangement to obtain substituted hydroxy-acetophenones which on condensation with phenylhydrazine gave the corresponding phenylhydrazones.

2-(5'-Chloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)indole: A mixture of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenonephenylhydrazone (26.5 g; 0.1 mole) and polyphosphoric acid (180 g; prepared from 120 g phosphorous pentoxide and 60 g orthophosphoric acid) was heated in an oil bath

at 120° for 1 hr with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temp. and then cold water (150 ml) was added to it. The product was filtered, washed with water and dried. Crystallization from ethanol gave pale yellow crystals, yield 16.3 g (66.9%), m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 69.2; H 4.2; N, 5.8. C₁₇H₁₄ClNO requires C, 68.94; H, 4.15; N, 5.75%). IR (KBr): 3400 ν(NH), 3275 ν(OH), 1610 cm⁻¹ ν(NH bending).

10-Chloro-6,6-dimethyl-6H-indolo[1,2-C] [1,3]benzoxazine (II): A mixture of 2-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)indole (6 g; 0.024 mole), *p*-toluenesulphonylchloride (0.05 g) and dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 50 hr. The solvent was distilled off under *vacuo* and the residue extracted with chloroform, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent and crystallization of the residue from ethanol gave the desired product, yield 3.6 g (54%), m.p. 138°. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.0; N, 5.0. C₁₇H₁₄ClNO requires C, 71.92; H, 4.95; N, 4.90%).

Biological activities:

Antibacterial activity: The antibacterial activity of all the compounds was tested against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* by disc diffusion method^{8,9}. The zone of inhibition as the diameter of each spot (mm), was measured after 24 hr and 48 hr with 0.1 mg/disc. The difference of diameter of the zone of inhibition of the test solution and that of the control gave the diameter of the actual zone of inhibition which was in the range 25 to 45 mm.

Antifungal activity: The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *H. sativum* and *A. alternata* by the tube dilution method⁷ and their minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined. It was observed that all the compounds were found to be moderately active at the concentration of 1 : 1000 against both the fungi.

Lethal dose fifty percent (LD₅₀): The 50% lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the compounds was determined by administering the solution of the compounds (12.5-3.2 mg/kg) in caudal vein of albino mice^{8,9} and the results were calculated by Karber's method¹⁰. It was observed that these compounds were very toxic.

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References

1. O. P. MALIK, R. S. KAPIL and N. ANAND, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 449.
2. O. P. MALIK, R. S. KAPIL and N. ANAND, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 455.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1968, p. 852.
4. M. MAHESHWARI, Ph.D. Thesis, Roorkee University, 1979.
5. R. S. VERMA and S. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1973, 13, 43.
6. K. C. AGRAWAL, *Indian J. Path.*, 1966, 45, 493.
7. J. M. VINCENT, *Farmer's Bull.*, U.S.D.A., *Inhibitor's Nature*, 159, 1950.
8. R. T. TURNER, "Screening Methods in Pharmacology", Academic Press, N. Y., London, 1965.
9. D. J. FINNEY, "Statistical Methods in Biological Assay", 3rd. Ed., Charles Griffin and Co. Ltd., London, 1978.
10. G. KARBER, *Arch. Exptl. Pathol. Pharmacol.*, 1931, 162, 480.

**Chemical Investigation of the Dry Fruits of
*Schrebera swietenoides***

(Miss) VIDYA and A. V. SUBBA RAO*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University,
Hyderabad-500 007

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accepted 1 September 1983*

SCHREBERA swietenoides Roxb. (Oleaceae) is a plant of average height (2-3 m) occurring in the tropics of Telangana and yields fruits in summer. The roots of this plant are reported to be used in the treatment of leprosy¹. In this communication we report the isolation of two known triterpene acids from the fruits of *S. swietenoides* which has not been previously investigated chemically.

Experimental

Plant material : The plant material was collected from Mananoor forest, 150 km south-east of Hyderabad.

Extraction and isolation of the constituents : The ground dry fruits of *S. swietenoides* were extracted with methanol by percolation. The extract on concentration and cooling furnished a solid residue. Silica gel chromatography of the solid resulted in the isolation of oleanolic acid and that of the mother liquor furnished betulinic acid.

The isolated compounds were identified by spectral data^{2,3} and comparison with authentic samples (superimposable ir, co-tlc). Derivatives of the isolated compounds, prepared to aid the

identification of the structures, included oleanolic acid acetate, methyl ester of oleanolic acid acetate, betulinic acid acetate and its methyl ester. Full details of the isolation and identification of the compounds are available on request.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., 1956, p. 223.
2. M. SHAMMA, R. E. GLICK and R. O. MUMMA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4512.
3. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, J. M. WILSON and C. DJERASSI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3688.

**Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace
Amounts of Tin(IV) with Diphenylcarbazone**

H. K. DAS and K. G. KAIMAL

Department of Chemistry, Gauhati University,
Gauhati-781 014

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accepted 19 July 1983*

NUMEROUS reagents have been proposed for spectrophotometric determination of tin but a few are suitable for common use. A simple, sensitive and selective extraction-photometric method for the determination of tin with diphenylcarbazone is described in this paper. The use of diphenylcarbazone as an analytical reagent has long been known. It forms chelate complexes with many heavy metals¹⁻⁴. Balt and Dalen⁴ found that Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Sn²⁺ form 1 : 2 complexes with diphenylcarbazone while Cu⁺ forms 1 : 1 and Fe²⁺ 1 : 3 complexes. In the present investigation, it is found that tin(IV) reacts with diphenylcarbazone in 1 N hydrochloric acid medium forming a rose-red coloured complex which is extractable into isobutyl methyl ketone. This forms the basis of the method.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made with a Beckmann DK-2 spectrophotometer in matched quartz cells of 1.0 cm optical path.

A stock solution was prepared by dissolving 2.995 g stannic chloride pentahydrate (B.D.H.) in 1 litre 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid. The amount of tin was estimated gravimetrically by the N-benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine method⁵. The solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by dilution of the stock solution and were made 1N with respect